

Original Research

Unveiling Drivers of Consumer Loyalty for Private Sector Commercial Bank Service in Colombo District, Sri Lanka

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Received 6 March 2025 Revised 10 August 2025 Accepted 17 August 2025

Abstract

The development of new services to meet consumer needs is becoming a crucial issue for the banking sector in Sri Lanka, as the rivalry within the sector is growing daily and services are rapidly becoming the driving forces of economies. Accordingly, current research is a comprehensive study of the identification of the determinants of consumer loyalty in the Private Sector Commercial Bank Service. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from 306 banking consumers. Data were analyzed using SPSS Software. Findings revealed that customer loyalty is positively influenced by trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value. Moreover, the results showed that the highest positive correlation of the level of customer loyalty was with customer satisfaction, the second-highest positive correlation was with corporate image and the lowest positive correlation was with commitment. The findings encourage Sri Lankan banks to employ technology to enhance customer satisfaction and service quality, which would enable them to handle contemporary challenges in a banking market.

Keywords: Commercial Banks, Consumer Loyalty, Determinants, Satisfaction.

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Introduction

Globally, the area of consumer loyalty within the banking sector has developed as a critical success factor for achieving and holding a considerable level of competitive advantage within this contemporary, increasingly digitalized environment (Mahfouz et al., 2025). In developed markets covering the areas of the UAE, the United States and Europe, the banking firms have started to use supportive technological innovations for enhancing customer loyalty, like AI-driven personalization, mobile banking and open banking frameworks (Yaseen & Al-Amarneh, 2025). They could reshape customer expectations, making seamless service delivery, and become a key driver of developing consumer loyalty (Deloitte, 2023; PwC, 2022). When considering the emerging economies, some authors from India and Brazil have indicated that the loyalty of the consumers is strongly influenced by perceived service quality, digital trust and perceived commitment of the banks on banking activities and particularly relating to fintech adoption (Sharma et al., 2024; Cardoso et al., 2022). While these global trends highlight the interplay between technology and loyalty, the dynamics may vary in Sri Lanka because of the existing differences relating to cultural attitudes of consumers towards banking activities, infrastructural readiness, and the pace of technological adoption.

Concerning the banking sector even in Sri Lanka, consumer loyalty is a critical point that has an impact on the stability of banks. A loyal customer for a bank is not only a one-time investment to the bank; it also will be the growth supplementary component (Karim et al., 2023). Customer loyalty is the method by which bank customers continue to use a product or service rather than preferring another bank to purchase their goods or services. Private Banks in Sri Lanka face considerable competition among them. Consumer loyalty is a critical factor in this research, and it is believed that a strong relationship with the customer can be combined. Due to highly innovative technology integration and competitiveness, many banks need to evaluate and identify the customer loyalty relationship structure (Ahmed et al., 2023).

The main objective of the research was to identify the determinants of customer loyalty in the private commercial banks of Sri Lanka. In line with the above objective, the researchers have identified five determinants such as trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value. According to the Central Bank of Sri Lanka (2024), digital transaction volumes of mobile and internet banking increased by 38% in 2023, while CEFTS interbank transfers increased by 45% year on year. A survey by LIRNEasia (2023) found that out of the banking customers surveyed, 72% find digital platforms more convenient and 68% report that service delivery has become quicker because of technological improvements. Such changes could have altered the factors driving customer loyalty, thus demonstrating the need to re-evaluate present loyalty determinants in the transformed service landscape of such major private banks in Sri Lanka. Having a considerable customer base and assets, six reputed local commercial banks in Sri Lanka, namely Sampath Bank, Commercial Bank, Seylan Bank, Nation Trust Bank, Pan Asia Bank, and Hatton National Bank play a vital role as domestic private retail (commercial) banks in Sri Lanka.

Several studies have been conducted for the identification of determinants of customer loyalty. However, the factors affecting consumer loyalty changed with the advancement

of technology and improved service quality. Accordingly, this study attempts to investigate the determinants of customer loyalty of private commercial banks in Sri Lanka.

Literature Review

Customer Loyalty

Selecting the products and services of a business over those of its competitors regularly is known as customer loyalty. According to Pandita and Mehta (2019) and Khan and Khan (2021), customer loyalty is considered a substantial and long-term intangible asset. Price or availability cannot readily affect a company's loyal customers. Consistently favourable emotional experiences, contentment with physical attributes, and the perceived value of an experience—including the goods or services—are the main drivers of customer loyalty (Godefroit-Winkel et al., 2022). Patronage behaviour and one's attitude towards an entity determine one's level of loyalty, claim Safer et al. (2021).

Customer loyalty, as defined by Lee and Wong (2021), is the sustained devotion of a customer to a brand, service, or product provided by a certain company. In addition, he describes loyalty as "a deeply held commitment to re-buy or re-patronize a preferred product/service consistently in the future thereby causing same repetitive brand or same-brand set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behaviour". There are three main ways to analyze consumer loyalty: the integrated method, the behavioral approach, and the attitudinal approach (Saini & Singh, 2020). The behavioral method looks at how consistently a customer has made purchases in the past. According to this method, the rate, frequency, and likelihood of a purchase are used to gauge customer loyalty. The attitude approach looks at how customers feel about a certain product or service, including their psychological engagement, favoritism, and goodwill. Additionally, this strategy aims to incorporate word-of-mouth (WOM).

However, the buyer may have a positive opinion of an item but stop buying it over time because they have a stronger opinion of competing brands. As a result, academics recommend using relative attitude to gauge loyalty. In a marketing setting, relative attitudes are measured using two dimensions: attitudinal differentiation and attitudinal strength. (Kusumawati & Rahayu, 2020). The integrated approach suggests that loyalty results from attitudes as well as behaviors. Accordingly, early researchers mentioned the inseparability of appraisal of the objects and repeated purchase behavior from loyalty.

Determinants of customer loyalty

Due to the notable increase in the banking industry's competitiveness, customer loyalty has grown in importance. To increase their profitability, banks must determine the elements that affect client loyalty. To develop different approaches for the elements that have a major impact on customer loyalty, bank management needs to identify and understand these elements. The current study's goal is to investigate the variables that impact customer loyalty in Sri Lanka's private commercial banks, with a focus on the Colombo region.

Trust

According to Morgan and Hunt (1994), trust is the capacity to rely on a trade partner who inspires confidence. Afterward, Alam et al. (2021) suggested that a crucial element of trust is the degree to which the client feels the vendor cares about achieving favorable results for them and has objectives and motives that are advantageous to them. Therefore, suppliers who seem more engaged in building trust than in welfare will be more likely to be trusted by consumers who care about positive customer outcomes. Customer loyalty and relationship commitment are significantly impacted by trust. The client can more confidently forecast the service supplier's future transactions when the service provider behaves in a way that fosters customer trust, hence lowering the perceived risk within the service provider. Consumer satisfaction and loyalty are strongly correlated with the degree to which a consumer perceives a service provider's values to be congruent with their own. This is how trust affects loyalty (Jenneboer et al., 2022). Customer base and securing long-term profitability. Customers expect the greatest confidence from the bank as they have their financial information.

Commitment

Commitment is a crucial component in assessing the strength of a marketing relationship, as well as a useful construct for predicting future purchase frequency and estimating the likelihood of customer loyalty (Kalia et al., 2021). According to their definition, commitment is the enduring want to preserve a meaningful relationship. This suggests a greater degree of responsibility to ensure that a relationship is fruitful, satisfying, and mutually beneficial. This suggests a greater degree of responsibility to ensure that a relationship is fruitful, satisfying, and mutually beneficial. As per Kim and Kim (2018), dedication plays a crucial role in fostering client loyalty. This involves attending to customers' demands, customizing items to meet their specifications, and maintaining a flexible approach to customer relationships. He suggested that banks should act appropriately and acknowledge the role that service dedication plays in retaining devoted clients.

Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is the extent to which a business's products and services meet or exceed the expectations of its customers. Recurring business is a reliable indicator of customer satisfaction with a company's products and services. The importance of happy consumers cannot be overstated, as they are free advertisements for businesses. Customer satisfaction is crucial in the business world, as a company cannot function without contented and loyal clients (Naini et al., 2022). Focusing more on client satisfaction and retention will bring us more long-term business. In the banking industry, client happiness is largely dependent on the type of relationship that exists between the customer and the provider of goods and services. As a result, it is generally accepted that retaining and attracting devoted customers requires offering high-quality products and services (Taufik, et al., 2022). Happy customers typically stay with a vendor, whereas dissatisfied customers look for another one. According to Lovelock and Wirtz (2010), the foundation of genuine loyalty is customer satisfaction (Dwita and Agustine, 2023). Marketing management states that customer happiness has the biggest impact on client loyalty.

Corporate Image

The way a company, organization, or commercial venture shows itself to the public is known as its corporate image. Aydin and Ozer (2005) state that a company's physical and behavioral characteristics, including its name, architecture, range of goods and services offered, and the sense of excellence that each employee conveys when engaging with the company's clientele, are all tied to its corporate image. The pictures show the caliber of the product and the company's standards (Ab Hamid et al., 2023). A bank's reputation, which is developed over time, is likely to have a big impact on the association between its operational excellence and customer loyalty and could be crucial in keeping clients. Banks can project a variety of images, including dependability in service provision, personnel politeness, worldwide connectivity, and occasionally a sense of national pride. The association between operational excellence and customer loyalty is anticipated to be significantly impacted by a bank's corporate image, which can play a critical role in client retention over time (Le, 2023).

Perceived Value

A consumer's overall assessment of a product's usefulness based on what they believe they received and have given to obtain it is known as perceived value (Nguyen et al., 2021). While value has been identified as a construct made up of multiple variables in the multidimensional approach, perceived value has been treated as an independent concept and quantified as a single variable in the unit-dimensional approach (Sanchez-Fernandez; Iniesta-Bonillo, 2007). If customers believe that the company's outcome-to-input ratio is similar to their own, they will be more inclined to feel that they have been treated fairly (Matsuoka, 2022). Put another way, clients frequently assess a business's return on investment by contrasting its offerings with those of its rivals in the marketplace. Four distinct layers comprise the composition of consumer value: price's economic worth, quality's functional value, emotional value, and social value. The term "economic value" refers to the monetary value that consumers place on reduced prices or expenses when comparing them to other options for goods or services. A product or service's emotional worth is determined by the feelings or emotions it evokes (Paulose & Shakeel, 2022). Thus, the degree to which people can use and purchase a product or service to socially communicate their image to others is represented by the concept of social value. When employing services, economic value is a crucial consideration. For example, by offering economic value, a technologically innovative banking service that does away with physical locations and gives users more financial advantages over traditional banks without employing counter-employers is likely to encourage people to adopt it.

Research Methodology

Conceptualization

The conceptual framework of the present study, with five independent variables: trust commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value, was developed based on the findings of Özkan et al. (2020), and Islam et al. (2021).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Operationalization

The dependent variable in this research study is consumer loyalty, which had six questions. The dimensions are listed in Table 1. The independent variables of this study are trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value. The independent variables had twenty questions in Part B.

Table 1. Operationalization of Variables

Variable	Dimension
Trust	i. Service
	ii. Privacy
	iii. efficient
	iv. Reputation
Commitment	i. Availability of information
	ii. Resource allocation
	iii. Relationship between the consumer and the bank
	iv. Growth of technological innovation
Satisfaction	i. Transaction speed
	ii. System availability
	iii. Ease of use
	iv. Accuracy of transaction
Corporate image	i. Media activities
	ii. Social responsibility

Variable	Dimension
	iii. Financial performance
	iv. Global activities
Perceived value	i. Cost
	ii. Fair charges
	iii. Value for money
	iv. Expectation
Consumer Loyalty	i. Word of mouth
	ii. Repeat Purchasing of services
	iii. Customer referrals

Population, Sample & Sampling Technique

The target population of the present study was 909,115 people in the Colombo district between the ages of 20 to 44 years, assuming that they all deal with selected private commercial banks and use technology innovations for day-to-day banking requirements. The participants of the study sample were chosen using simple random sampling. 384 people were determined as the sample from a population using Krejcie and Morgan's table.

The Colombo district is intentionally chosen as the geographical focus, given that it is the most urbanized, economically active region in Sri Lanka with all the headquarters and primary operations of the major private commercial banks being there. It also shows the highest uptake rates in the usage of digital banking services, and as such, it is an ideal context for technology-linked loyalty dynamics. While this would limit generalizability to the other districts, the concentration of target behaviors in Colombo enhances the internal validity of the study.

Data Collection and Analysis

A systematic questionnaire was used to gather the primary data for the study and the validated customer loyalty measurement scale created by Veloso and Monte (2019) and Bobâlcă et al. (2012) was modified. Simple linear regression and correlation analysis were used to examine the data. This simple linear regression analysis was used by the authors to isolate the individual effect of each determinant of this study, providing clarity on their independent contributions

To provide a clearer understanding, the used simple regression equation is presented below. That model has used for each independent variable separately in the data analysis process. In each case, Consumer Loyalty (Y) serves as the dependent variable, while Trust, Commitment, Satisfaction, Corporate Image, and Perceived Value are the predictors tested individually.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y = Consumer Loyalty

α = Constant (intercept)

β = Unstandardized coefficient of the independent variable

X = Independent variable

ε = Error term

Findings

Reliability and Validity

The reliability of inter-item consistency was evaluated using the Cronbach's Alpha test. The analysis reached a suitable reliability level, and Table 2 below displays the results of the Cronbach's alpha test.

Table 2. Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Trust	.705
Commitment	.798
Satisfaction	.699
Corporate image	.603
Perceived value	.772
Consumer Loyalty	.779

According to the findings provided in Table 2, all variables have adequate reliability levels which have exceeded 0.6 (Hwui & Lay, 2018), as shown by the fact that their Cronbach's Alpha values above the minimal requirement of 0.6. The results show that the measurement items for each variable are consistent and appropriate for further analysis, which guarantees that the conclusions of the research are reliable.

Table 2: Validity

Variable	KMO Value	df	Sig.
Trust	0.731	6	0.000
Commitment	0.779	6	0.000
Satisfaction	0.695	6	0.000
Corporate Image	0.662	6	0.000
Perceived Value	0.726	6	0.000
Consumer Loyalty	0.809	15	0.000

The validity was assessed using Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy. The KMO values for the research variables were between 0.662 and 0.809, which means that the sample size was enough for factor analysis since all of the values were more than the expected limit for the factor analysis of 0.5 (Shkeer & Awang, 2019). These findings verify that the data was sufficient for recognizing significant patterns and correlations between variables. The findings of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) for all variables, indicating that there are strong correlations among the variables and that factor analysis is appropriate for conducting this study.

Demographic Profiles of the Respondents

Table 4. Demographic Data

Category	Subcategory	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	42.8
	Female	57.2
Age Group (Years)	25-29	53.0
	30-34	25.0
	35-39	22.0
Education Level	Undergraduate	44.4
	Graduate and above	26.5
	G.C.E. (A/L)	28.1
Occupational Status	Full-Time Employee	47.4
	Unemployed	10.3
	Other	42.3
Monthly Income (LKR)	<25,000	52.3
	25,001-50,000	12.7
	>50,000	35.0
Preferred Transaction	Online Banking	77.1
	Mobile Banking	22.9
Frequently Used Banks	Sampath Bank	32.7
	Commercial Bank	25.0
	Others	42.3
Innovative Services Use	Weekly	48.7
	Monthly	32.0
	Annually	19.3

The conducted survey for this study was focused on 384 clients from chosen banks established in Sri Lanka, and 306 replies were obtained from the respondents, resulting in an 80% response rate. The demographic and behavioral profile of responders gives useful information into how customers interact with mobile payment systems. Of the people who answered the survey, 57.2% were female and 42.8% were male. The 25-29 age group made up the largest percentage (53%), followed by the 30-34 age group (25%),

while the 35-39 age group made up the smallest percentage (22%). In terms of education levels, 44.4% of the individuals were undergraduates, 26.5% had graduate or higher credentials, and 28.1% had finished G.C.E. (A/L). In terms of employment, 47.4% of people were working full-time, while the lowest category was made up of jobless persons, who made up 10.3% of the total. The income levels were different, with 52.3% of those earning less than LKR 25,000 per month, 12.7% earning between LKR 25,001 and LKR 50,000, and the remaining 35% earning more than LKR 50,000.

The majority of people preferred internet banking for their transactions, while mobile banking was the preferred method for 22.9% of people. Sampath Bank was the most popular bank, with 32.7% of respondents choosing it. Commercial Bank was the second most popular. Pan Asia Bank and Seylan Bank were the banks that were utilized the least. The usage of innovative financial services found that 48.7% of respondents used these services weekly, while the least frequent users interacted with them yearly. These results provide a complete overview of the demographic and behavioral characteristics of the respondents, offering important information for future initiatives that seek to improve consumer engagement with banking services in Sri Lanka.

Simple Regression Analysis

The simple regression analysis that was conducted for this study highlighted the existing associations between various independent variables including trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value and consumer loyalty. The results of this analysis were revealed significant findings, indicating that all predictors positively and significantly associating and influencing consumer loyalty, which is displayed a summary of the analysis in the following table.

Table 5. Results of the Simple Regression Analysis

Variable	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error	β	t	Sig. (p)	Variance Explained (%)
Trust	0.520	0.270	0.267	2.30012	0.520	10.702	0.000	27.0
Commitment	0.445	0.198	0.195	2.5035	0.445	8.675	0.000	19.8
Satisfaction	0.610	0.372	0.370	2.15028	0.610	13.810	0.000	37.2
Corporate Image	0.600	0.360	0.357	2.16589	0.600	13.402	0.000	36.0
Perceived Value	0.540	0.292	0.290	2.30000	0.540	12.285	0.000	29.2

Trust and Consumer Loyalty

Trust was shown to be a significant predictor of customer loyalty within this study, with an R-square value of 0.270, which means it could be explained 27% of the variation

in consumer loyalty. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.520$, $p < 0.001$) shows that there is a moderate positive association between trust and customer loyalty. This means that if trust increases by one unit, consumer loyalty also has the ability to rise by 0.520 units.

The positive association found between the variables of trust and customer loyalty is supported by the findings of Nguyen and Mutum (2012). The authors have regard trust of the consumers as the basis for lasting customer relationships in the service sector. Under the Sri Lanka private banks' setup, high trust may be alleviating perceived risk regarding financial transactions via the digital channel, all conducive to repeat usage (Samarasinghe et al., 2020). This explains trust being a psychological safety net ensuring loyalty despite external market pressures.

Commitment and Consumer Loyalty

Commitment also had reported a considerable impact on determining the level of customer loyalty, with an R-square value of 0.198, which means that it explained 19.8% of the variation in the level of customer loyalty. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.445$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that there is a positive link between commitment and loyalty. Specifically, an increase of one unit in commitment leads to an increase of 0.445 units in loyalty.

The positive contribution of commitment as per the results, is in agreement with the findings of Rahi and Ghani (2021), who were stressed that the more committed the customers are, the more likely they will stick with the banks in the long run, even when offered alternatives. In the particular case of the private banking sector in Sri Lanka, the investment in the relationship, e.g., personalization of services or taking into account an account history, may impose switching costs. Nevertheless, although lesser than satisfaction, commitment creates loyalty by deepening relational bonds, stretching beyond transactional rewards.

Satisfaction and Consumer Loyalty

Satisfaction had reported the best and highest predictive value of all the variables within the tested regression model, with an R-square of 0.372, which means it explained 37.2% of the variation in the level of customer loyalty. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.610$, $p < 0.01$) suggests a significant positive association, where a unit increase in satisfaction translates in a 0.610 unit increase in loyalty.

Satisfaction's dominant role as indicated in the results supports Islam et al. (2021), who argue that satisfaction is often the strongest loyalty driver in services due to its direct influence on emotional attachment and repurchase intentions. Thus, when considering Sri Lanka's private banking sector, having a superior service quality, problem resolution, and positive branch/digital experiences may explain its lead over other predictors (Lakchan & Samaraweera, 2023). Satisfaction's breadth captures multiple service touchpoints, making it a comprehensive loyalty determinant.

Corporate Image and Consumer Loyalty

Corporate image was another powerful predictor, with an R-squared value of 0.360, which means that it accounted for 36% of the variation in loyalty. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.600$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that a unit rise in corporate image results in a 0.600 unit increase in loyalty, which means that there is a positive influence.

The positive association relating to consumer behavior replicate the findings of the authors of Kim and Kim (2018), who argued that brands create loyalty through the pride and trust that a positive image instills in customers. In the Sri Lankan private banking sector, an image viewed as being with good repute from CSR, ethical behavior, and innovations could perhaps rival satisfaction as a significant predictor, especially in a market where image is used as a tool to be viewed as a signal of stability a highly valued factor in ever-trusting industries such as banking.

Perceived Value and Consumer Loyalty

Perceived value accounted for 29.2% of the variation in loyalty, with an R-square of 0.292. The standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.540$, $p < 0.001$) shows that there is a moderate positive association, which means that if perceived value increases by one unit, loyalty will rise by 0.540 units.

The positive association between perceived value and customer goes along with the insights published by Khan et al. (2021). The authors stating that customers judge loyalty according to the benefits received for a cost. Interest rates, fee structures, and service bundles may increase perceived value within Sri Lanka's banking sector. Although it plays a less important role than satisfaction or corporate image, perceived value stands apart as it relates rational evaluation and adds to the other factors of loyalty which flow more from emotional and relational concerns.

Correlation analysis

The level of association between driving factors and customer loyalty was measured using correlation analysis. The findings of the correlation analysis of the study are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Summary of the Correlation Analysis

Variables	Correlation coefficient (r)	Sig. Value (p)
Trust & Customer Loyalty	0.520	0.000
Commitment & Customer Loyalty	0.445	0.001
Satisfaction & Customer Loyalty	0.610	0.000
Corporate Image & Customer Loyalty	0.600	0.001
Perceived Value & Customer Loyalty	0.540	0.000

According to the correlation study also, all of the variables have a positive and statistically significant connection with customer loyalty ($p < 0.05$), meaning that when these aspects get better, customer loyalty tends to get better as well.

Table 7. Results of Hypothesis Testing

H ₁ : There is a positive association between Relationship between trust and consumer loyalty	Accepted
H ₂ : There is a positive association between commitment and consumer loyalty	Accepted
H ₃ : There is a positive association between satisfaction and consumer loyalty	Accepted
H ₄ : There is a positive association between corporate image and consumer loyalty	Accepted
H ₅ : There is a positive association between perceived value and customer loyalty	Accepted

According to the findings of the correlation analysis depicted in Table 6 and the regression analysis shown in Table 5, the tests are significant ($p < 0.05$) and all are accepted. Accordingly, it was revealed that there are positive associations between trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, perceived value, and customer loyalty.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The findings of the present study revealed that customer loyalty is positively influenced by trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value. Moreover, the results showed that the highest positive correlation of the level of customer loyalty was with satisfaction, the second-highest positive correlation was with corporate image, and the lowest positive correlation was with commitment. As per the findings of the study results, the top-level positions and policymakers in commercial banks in Sri Lanka need to implement viable strategies to increase customer satisfaction, the corporate image of the bank, and commitment to the customers.

Customer satisfaction of the customers in the banking industry is influenced by transaction speed, system availability, ease of use, and accuracy of the transaction. Hence, using technological innovations, bankers can uplift the aforesaid expectations of the banking customers. Amarathunga and Pathiratna (2016) revealed that banking customers are more satisfied with the services delivered through new and innovative technology. The banks can introduce various technological innovations that affect consumer loyalty is satisfaction. "Mobile banking, online banking, and ATMs are comfortable and flexible to use. This is a highly impacted question for satisfaction. Doing the transactions via technologically innovative banking services is more flexible and comfortable. Banks need to build greater customer relationship management among innovative banking customers by ensuring that the bank is always there to support consumers and give attention to their needs. Every bank has to their attention to allocating the financial resources, human resources, and other technological innovations, as well as doing more and more research and development projects to improve and develop the quality of technological innovation services according to the rapid growth of technology and communication environment. It

will be a significant decision to provide easy and friendly instructions to follow whenever customers use innovative banking services. Including sufficient, completed instructions on the websites and other communication apps is very important. This can be largely practiced through putting nonverbal cues such as images or short words or short messages, or whatever, and it should not be complicated. This helps banks to increase their customer base and to develop a loyal customer base.

Further, bankers needed to implement necessary strategies for improving corporate image, as that is also a significant determinant of customer loyalty, based on the findings of the present research. Moreover, as the study results have found, the corporate image of an organization fosters customer loyalty. When considering enhancing corporate image timely and valuable for fulfilling the social expectations of the consumers. Furthermore, younger generations are always environmentally conscious. Banks must develop eco-friendly technical advancements that protect the environment to attract their interest. Banks should keep in mind that they frequently have to focus on the younger generation due to their distinct traits, needs, and sensitivities. Moreover, banks should implement strategies not only for uplifting customer loyalty but also for increasing the productivity of the employees in the banking industry. Even the office design of the bank affects to increase in the productivity of the employees in the bank.

Implications of the Study

Theoretical Implications

This research makes a substantial contribution to the current body of information in the fields of consumer loyalty and financial services. The research improves theoretical frameworks that study consumer behavior in the banking industry by identifying and assessing the factors that determine customer loyalty, such as trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value. The results are consistent with and build upon current theories, such as Relationship Marketing and Service Quality models, by placing them in the context of the competitive and technology-driven environment of Sri Lankan private commercial banks. In addition, the research highlights the fact that customer loyalty is always changing in a financial industry that is expanding quickly. It places special emphasis on the relationship between conventional loyalty determinants and new technology innovations. It emphasizes the significance of combining digital banking advances with loyalty frameworks, pointing out a gap in previous research and providing a basis for future studies to investigate the impact of digital transformation and customer loyalty in developing countries.

Real-World Consequences

The results of this study have important practical consequences for private commercial banks in Sri Lanka. To begin with, they provide a strategic roadmap that focuses on trust, commitment, satisfaction, corporate image, and perceived value in order to improve client loyalty. Banks may develop trust with their customers by investing in tailored services, clear communication, and trustworthy digital platforms. In addition, loyalty programs, improved service delivery, and policies that prioritize customers may help to increase long-term involvement by encouraging commitment. The report also emphasizes the

significance of preserving a strong business image by means of consistent branding, corporate social responsibility efforts, and competitive service offers. Furthermore, banks may provide services that are both affordable and of good quality by taking into account the perceived value from the client's viewpoint. This helps them to meet consumer expectations. In a market that is very competitive, these insights allow private banks to set themselves apart from their competitors, keep their customers, and guarantee long-term success. Additionally, the results urge banks in Sri Lanka to use technology to improve the quality of their services and customer happiness, which will help them meet modern difficulties in a banking environment that prioritizes digital solutions.

Limitations and Avenues for Further Studies

Respondents who use the banking services of six Sri Lankan banks are included in this survey. Furthermore, a small number of public and private commercial banks are providing more interactive services to their clients. The selection of the sample is restricted to the Colombo district, and so that is not suitable to generalization an option to another district as social, technological, economic, and educational factors about the other districts vary from than Colombo district. Most of the surveyed respondents do not allocate adequate time to give the answers, and because of it, they tended to give neutral answers to the questionnaires. This research study considers generic factors rather than specific technological innovations, while each technologically innovative banking service is associated with different kinds of dimensions and expectations. The study has employed simple linear regression as the main analysis tool to examine the association of each determinant independently. Even though this approach clarifies individual effects effectively, it usually fails to account for potential multicollinearity or interactions between variables, such as trust and satisfaction. Future studies should apply multiple regression to enhance analytical robustness and explanatory power. Accordingly, future researchers are suggested to conduct the study by expanding the geographical area of the target population as well as considering both private sector and public sector commercial banks in Sri Lanka. That facilitates making comparisons of the level of customer loyalty in the private sector and public sector commercial banks in Sri Lanka.

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Amarathunga, P. and Kumarasinghe, H. (2026). Unveiling Drivers of Consumer Loyalty for Private Sector Commercial Bank Service in Colombo District, Sri Lanka. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 13(1), 18-37. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.505097.1690</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_236930.html</p>	